

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES - AS AN EFFECTIVE METHOD IN THE MEANINGFUL ORGANIZATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the effective aspects of using educational technologies in the educational system. And especially the effectiveness of using educational technologies and their specific types in elementary school mathematics lessons are discussed about.*

Keywords: *educational technologies, elementary school, mathematics, elements of algebra, teaching elements of algebra, non-traditional educational technologies.*

In any modern system of general education, mathematics is undoubtedly distinguished by the uniqueness of this field of knowledge and certainly occupies one of the main places. The questions like why mathematics is often needed? What is mathematics? are often met. The answer to such questions will be given differently by the teacher depending on the level of development of the student and the educational needs.

Thus, mathematics makes it possible to form certain forms of thoughts necessary for studying the surrounding world. On this basis, it is appropriate to pay attention to the issue of using educational technologies in teaching elements of algebra in elementary mathematics classes.

Today, every teacher is looking for the most effective ways to improve the learning process and increase the interest of students. If the student's activity in the class is not important for him, if he is bored and indifferent, he will not be able to show his abilities.

The use of a systematic-activity approach in educating students based on certain rules of general education means the opportunity to achieve the necessary result. Therefore, the choice of the most effective educational technologies depends on many factors (age of students, their capabilities, teacher's training, availability of different conditions, etc.). Effective, creative, research, design technologies and others should be prioritized. The goal of modern education is to educate a person with abilities such as comprehensively developed creativity and leadership. Modern and active educational technologies will help in the realization of this goal.

Educational technologies have always been an important part of the educational process and effectively served to enrich the content of education. The current state of the education system is characterized by the increasing role of non-traditional educational technologies. Learning by students with their help is much faster than with traditional technologies. These technologies change the nature of knowledge development, acquisition and dissemination, allow to deepen and expand the content of the studied subjects, quickly updating it, using more effective teaching methods, as well as significantly increasing the educational opportunities for each student.

Educational technologies are considered to be one of the effective methods of meaningful organization of primary school mathematics lessons. This can be seen as an example in teaching

the elements of algebra. In order to teach the elements of algebra to a group of students, to achieve results in explanatory work, a specialist must have a high level of knowledge. Because it is necessary to know what type of educational technology to use and where to apply it when teaching elements of algebra in mathematics lessons, and to be able to predict the long-term expected result. Based on this, the use of educational technologies expands the possibility of achieving results in the teaching process.

Today, every teacher is looking for the most effective ways to improve the learning process and increase the interest of students. If the student's activity in the class is not important for him, if he is bored and indifferent, he will not be able to show his abilities. Taking into account these aspects, it is required from the specialist who conducts teaching activities in primary education to pay attention to many factors in order to organize educational processes in a form rich in content.

Practice shows that knowledge of educational technologies is not enough, they should be implemented for a long time. It is always necessary to take into account that educational technology is a system of operation of all components of the pedagogical process, built on a scientific basis, programmed in time and space and leading to the intended results.

Among the various modern educational technologies, it is not inappropriate to highlight those that can be used in working with primary school students and, mainly, in teaching algebra elements in primary school mathematics classes. These can be adequately explained in the following order:

- critical thinking technology;
- health-saving technologies;
- Information and computer technologies (ICT);
- technology of design and research activities;
- person-oriented development technology;
- technology of differentiating levels of education;
- cooperation technology (group work, pair work, team work);
- game, information and communication, problem-based educational technology;
- developmental educational technology.

The use of the same educational technologies in elementary school mathematics lessons greatly helps students to awaken the basis of the concepts of algebra elements, to understand them more deeply, and to independently express what they consciously understand. It should also be noted that the appropriate use of educational technologies in the primary education of the general education system, especially in mathematics classes, will greatly help in strengthening the students' mathematical knowledge. In addition, it is one of the most effective ways to deepen students' knowledge of elements of algebra in mathematics classes, and to improve their current state. It is very important for a teacher who is teaching science only to be able to foresee which educational technology should be used in which part of the lesson and what results can be achieved after using it.

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